
PHYSICAL, PROXIMATE AND SENSORY COMPOSITION OF BISCUITS PRODUCED FROM WHEAT SUPPLEMENTED WITH FENUGREEK SEED FLOUR.

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ABSTRACT

The study presents the physical, proximate and organoleptic composition of biscuit produced from wheat flour and fenugreek seed flour. Material were collected, cleaned and sorted. Further processing of the materials into their respective flour before proceeding to produce the biscuit in four different varieties as seen in the study. Equipment and apparatus of standard quality was used for the production and analysis. Samples were produced and coded as AOA – Biscuit produced from 100% wheat flour, AOB – Biscuit produced from 97% wheat flour, 3% fenugreek flour, AOC – Biscuit produced from 95% wheat flour, 5% fenugreek flour, AOD – Biscuit produced from 93% wheat flour, 7% fenugreek flour. Physical characteristics was analysed to check for diameter, volume, spread ratio, thickness and weight. Result obtained showed sample AOD had the highest value for volume (162.21 ± 0.08), thickness and diameter (4.01 ± 0.32) and (4.20 ± 0.10) respectively. Sample AOA was observed to have the highest value for weight (400.20 ± 0.62) and density (2.80 ± 0.13). Cracks were not observed in the samples except for Sample AOC with slight cracks. Proximate analysis showed that sample AOD had the highest score for ash (1.05 ± 0.21) while sample AOB was observed to have significant increase at $p < 0.05$ for moisture (26.04 ± 0.01) and fiber (4.88 ± 0.10). Protein level was observed to be high in sample AOD (10.72 ± 0.01). Which carbohydrate content and energy value showed significant increase in sample AOC at (53.94 ± 0.18) and (86769.00 ± 0.62) respectively. Sensory analysis showed preference for Sample AOA has the highest score for taste (8.2) indicating the biscuit is most acceptable in taste preferences than the other. Similarly sample AOA

had the maximum score (8.4) for flavour. Sample AOD reportedly show maximum score (8.5) for texture . However sample AOA secured the highest score (8.7) for overall acceptability. There is need to ascertain a high level of sanitary hygiene, incorporating viable substitute and also carry out more recommended analysis to further improve in knowledge of biscuit production.

INTRODUCTION

Biscuit is a baked flour confectionary dried down to low moisture content (Hooda and Jood, 2005). It is principal food throughout the world, which gives more nutrients than any other single food source. (Bahatia *et al.*, 2008). Biscuit is mainly made from cereals, sweeteners, shortenings and leaving agent. Wheat is the most widely used cereals for biscuit making in that it provides necessary gluten to the biscuit structure. The quality of biscuits depends on quantity and quality of ingredients, especially the flour. It was found that mixing two or more different materials will help to solve the deficiency problem of cereals as low nutritional value by using legumes as food protein source. The use of legume protein is also limited to the protein of soybean seeds. Studies should now focus on a search for proteins from other sources, such as Fenugreek.

Fenugreek currently attracts research and commercial attention mainly due to high content of protein (20-25%), lysine (5-6%), soluble (20%) and insoluble dietary fiber (Pandey and Awasthi, 2015). Addition, it also possesses hypocholesterolemia and hypoglycemic properties. It has been reported that these seeds are cheap source of good quality protein and maybe mixed with cereals as a supplement for some limiting amino acids and hence for improving their protein quality through amino acid balance. Hence, development and consumption of such therapeutic bakery products would help to raise the nutritional status of the population. Having fenugreek seed as such in diet is not acceptable due to the distinct bitter taste; therefore; inclusion of fenugreek seed flour in such recipes that mask the bitter taste of fenugreek seed is a simple way to consume it.

Wheat flour is the principal component of nearly all biscuits and major advances in technology of flour milling coincided with the development of biscuit manufacturing. However, this study was designed to develop biscuits using fenugreek seed as base material and to investigate the effects of germinated fenugreek seed flour on quality parameters of biscuits in terms of physical, proximate and sensory characteristics.

Sample Preparation

Wheat Flour Production

Wheat flour was produced from whole wheat, production of wheat flour was achieved by cleaning the wheat grains by handpicking out the foreign matters, dirt and debris which was found in the wheat grains in order to avoid contamination, after the wheat grain was soaked in water for about an hour, this process was done in order to loose and make the wheat grain softer, the wheat grain was oven dried, the wheat is then passed through a single coarse milling machine where it was grounded up into a flour

Fenugreek Flour Production

Fenugreek flour production starts by cleaning seeds, this process is done to remove foreign materials like sand, grots and dirt that might be present in the fenugreek. After cleaning, the fenugreek undergoes conditioning which is the process of adding water to the fenugreek seed and allowing it to soak for some hours, after which is dried and milled with a milling machine where it was grounded into flour, the flour was sieved and then allowed to cool, it was set aside for further production or processing

Biscuit Production

Production of biscuits start with the weighing of ingredients, ingredients must be weighed to fulfill product recipe specification and quality requirements. After he roughly mixing of the wet and dry ingredients to form a thick dough, the dough is rolled out on a neat flat surface according to the desired height of the biscuit, then the dough is divided into individual sizes using a biscuit cutter, then baked in an oven for quality biscuit production.

Wheat flour, Fenugreek Seed flour

Weighing of ingredients

Mixing

Kneading

Proofing

Rolling

Cutting

Panning

Baking

Cooling

Biscuit

Fig 1: Flow chart showing Biscuit Production Supplemented with Fenugreek Seed flour.

Sample Formulation

SAMPLE	WHEAT FLOUR%	FENUGREEK SEED FLOUR %
AOA	100	-
AOB	97	3
AOC	95	5
AOD	93	7

Keys

AOA – Biscuit produced with 100% Wheat flour

AOB- Biscuit produced with 97% Wheat flour and 3% fenugreek flour

AOC- Biscuit produced with 95% Wheat flour and 5% fenugreek flour

AOD - Biscuit produced with 93% Wheat flour and 7% fenugreek flour

Methods

The Physical and Proximate Analysis was determined using the standard methods as described by (FAO, 2012). while the hedonic scale was used to evaluate the sensory characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Table 1 Physical Characteristics of different biscuit sample

Parameters	AOA	AOB	AOC	AOD
Volume(ml)	142.75±0.12	141.10±0.16	147.70±0.41	162.21±0.08
Weight (g)	400.20±0.62	340.90±0.04	355.01±0.20	232.40±0.16
Spread Ratio	0.47±0.21	1.59±0.18	1.52± 0.22	1.04±0.11
Density(g/ml)	2.80±0.13	2.42±0.01	2.40±0.13	1.43±0.12
Thickness(mm)	3.34±0.04	3.76±0.10	3.60±0.15	4.01±0.32
Diameter(mm)	1.60±0.21	3.80±0.00	3.65±0.10	4.20±0.10
Crack formation	No crack	No crack	Slight cracks	No cracks

Table 2. Table Showing the Proximate Analysis of Biscuit Samples Values are triplicate determination of mean \pm standard deviation

Parameters	AOA	AOB	AOC	AOD	LSD
Ash(%)	0.52 ^c ±0.01	0.34 ^b ±0.02	0.94 ^{ab} ±0.17	1.06 ^a ±0.21	0.13
Moisture (%)	22.23 ^b ±0.20	26.04 ^a ±0.01	11.37 ^d ±0.04	15.07 ^c ±0.08	1.59
Crude Fibre(%)	0.58 ^c ±0.06	4.88 ^a ±0.10	2.72 ^b ±0.06	2.99 ^b ±0.40	0.86
Lipid(%)	14.60 ^c ±0.00	19.71 ^b ±0.01	25.34 ^a ±0.01	25.31 ^a ±0.00	0.24
Protein(%)	6.13 ^c ±0.02	6.35 ^b ±0.10	5.60 ^d ±0.00	10.72 ^a ±0.01	0.32
Carbohydrate(%)	55.86 ^a ±0.28	42.18 ^a ±0.14	53.94±0.18	44.85 ^c ±0.20	1.90
Energy	70614.47 ^c	70339.62 ^d	88769.00 ^a	31860.46 ^b	5.01
Value (Kj/100g)	±0.32	±0.48	±0.62	±1.02	

Table 3. Table Showing the Sensory Evaluation of Biscuit Samples Values are triplicate determination of mean \pm standard deviation

Sample	Taste	Flavour	Texture	General Acceptability
AOA	8.2 ^{ab}	8.4 ^a	7.5 ^b	8.7 ^a
AOB	7.1 ^b	7.8 ^b	8.0 ^{ab}	8.2 ^{ab}
AOC	8.5 ^a	7.9 ^{ab}	7.9 ^{ab}	8.1 ^{ab}
AOD	7.9 ^{ab}	7.4 ^{ab}	8.5 ^a	7.9 ^{ab}
LSD	0.1124	0.3126	0.2146	0.2611

DISCUSSION

Table 1. The result obtained from the physical characteristics of the produced biscuit from various proportion of wheat flour and fenugreek flour as stipulated in the table 4.1. it can be deduced from the table that

the volume of the biscuits varied for each sample. Sample AOD (162.21 ± 0.08) was observed to have the highest volume while sample AOA (141.10 ± 0.16). The volume of biscuit is measured by the multiplication of the area and the diameter of the biscuit FAO (2004) stipulated that the volume of biscuit describes the level of its quantity and the space it occupies. Volume plays a major role in the substantiality of a snack thus a viable indicator that lays emphasis on the snack. Weight showed an increased in significance with sample AOA (400.20 ± 0.62) having the highest value while sample AOD has the lowest. The weight is a significant parameter that describes the quantity of constituent found in a given sample thus making sample AOA having the most adequate supply of constituent make up. The weight describes the bulking nature of the snack which is proportional to the constituent and composition of the snack. Wheat flour exhibits bulky characteristics which attributes to sample AOA having the highest value for weight. The spread ratio is a function of the quotient of the diameter against the thickness of the biscuit. The result obtained showed that sample AOB (1.59 ± 0.18) was observed to have the highest value for spread ratio at a significant level while sample AOA (0.47 ± 0.21) had the least value.

This results correlates with results obtained from Singh (2008) who developed high protein biscuits from green gram flour. Density which is a function of the weight of the sample and the volume of the sample AOD (1.43 ± 0.12) having the least density from the table. The result also showed that sample The thickness was measured using the Vernier caliper, it was observed that sample AOA (3.34 ± 0.04) had the least value for thickness which can be attributed to the filling of the baking batter and the dough rise while sample AOD had the highest (4.01 ± 0.32) as seen in the result. The diameter was measured and the result showed that sample AOD (4.20 ± 0.10) had the highest value while sample AOA had the least value (1.60 ± 0.21). Antia (2006) describes the formation of cracks on baked snacks as a result of the coarseness of the batter. Cracks were checked on the cookies to ascertain the smoothness of the batter, the result showed that sample

AOC had slight cracks while the other samples were observed to have cracks after baking.

Table 2 represents the proximate analysis of biscuit sample produced from wheat flour and fenugreek flour. It can be inferred from the result that the ash content ranged from (0.52 ± 0.07) to (1.06 ± 0.21) with sample AOA having the least value and sample AOD having the highest value sharing significant difference at $p < 0.05$. The increase in ash content on the sample was observed as the percentage of fenugreek flour increased in the sample. Thus result is in line with (Missodi *et al.*, 2002) who observed the same increase with jackfruit flour when blended with wheat flour for biscuit production. The moisture content is an indicator for the availability of free water and bound water present in a sample. (Amin *et al.*, 2001). It is a measure of water activity in a sample. It is an indicator for controlling microbial infestation and proliferation which is a strong attribute for food spoilage. From the result, it can be deduced that sample AOC (11.37 ± 0.04) had the lowest score thus a low possibility of quick spoilage and longer shelf life as compared to sample AOB (26.04 ± 0.01) having the highest score and thus prone to spoilage and low shelf life. Notably, moisture content plays a major role in understanding the shelf life and sustainability of a sample.

Crude fiber was observed to be significantly high in sample AOB (4.88 ± 0.10) with sample AOA (0.58 ± 0.06) which is the lowest score for crude fiber in the analysis. It is suggested that the addition of fenugreek flour invariably influenced the crude fiber content of the sample. The result corresponds with (Lu *et al.*, 2010) who has a similar research in the production of cookies using coconut flour to blend wheat. Crude fiber is an indicator of dietary fiber in food and roughages which are seen as organics that aid in food digestibility. The lipid content increased significantly across the sample with sample AOB (25.31 ± 0.00) having the highest score which can be attributed to the oil obtained from the fenugreek flour present in the sample. Moreover, the fenugreek wasn't fattened before usage thus the increased trend as the flour increased in the samples. the fat level is significantly high and the

infusion of a fat substitute for the baking pours influenced the lipid content. (Esteller *et al.*, 2004). Sample AOB has a significant increase in protein content (10.72 ± 0.01) as compared to other samples. Protein finally breaks to amino acids which as absorbed by the body cells to prim functions such as cell regeneration, tissues repair, cell maturation and regeneration, tissue repair, cell maturation and differentiation (Attia, 2005). Protein as macro-nutrient constituent the body-building capacity of the food sample. Protein aids in the repair of worn out cells and tissue; replenish dead cells and aids in the building of body cells. Biscuits rich in protein are nourished diet and thus deal for consumption. Carbohydrate level leads the highest in sample AOA (55.86 ± 0.28). Carbohydrate showed little variation among the sample. Carbohydrates are most abundant of all organic compounds in the biosphere and this class of compounds is literally tagged "hydrate of carbon" which provides energy to the body. Carbohydrate as a major source of energy has been known to be a high calorific food substance. It plays a major role in blood sugar regulation, sparing the use of proteins for energy, biological recognition processes and as flavours/sweetners. The energy value (kj/ 100g) is in relationship to a quantity of kilojoules calculated for a gram of nutrient in food sample. Sample AOC (86769.00 ± 0.62) Kj/100g has the highest energy value. Table 3. shows the sensory evaluation of the produced varieties of the biscuit samples made from proportions of wheat flour and fenugreek flour. The mean score for taste, flavour, texture and overall acceptability preference were recorded. It revealed that there were significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in flavour, texture and overall acceptability among the biscuit samples. Sample AOA has the highest score for taste (8.2) indicating the biscuit is most acceptable in taste preferences than the other. Similarly sample AOA had the maximum score (8.4) for flavour. Sample AOD reportedly show maximum score (8.5) for texture. Sobukola *et al.* (2010) reportedly that wheat flour complemented with snail meat flour resulted in biscuits with acceptable sensory preferences. However sample AOA secured the highest score (8.7) for overall acceptability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The research was carried on the nutrient evaluation of biscuit produced from wheat-fenugreek meat flour. It can be observed that the formulation ratio produced a wide variety of the biscuit sample as seen in the result obtained from the analysis. The proximate analysis showed great result variation as seen in the protein content and ash content which increased as the proportion of fenugreek flour increased in the biscuit sample. Physical characteristics showed a conventional value in the density, spread ratio and thickness of the samples. Sample AOA showed overall acceptability in the terms of taste, flavor and texture. It can be concluded that the incorporation of fenugreek flour in the mixture greatly improved the biscuit nutritional composition. More so, the study was limited, thus the need to carry out further analysis such as mineral analysis, rheological properties, vitamin profile and microbial isolation so as to ascertain the level of safety of the sample and also to contribute immensely to the knowledge of the biscuit varieties.

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